

ELIXIR Service Bundle: Systems Biology for Rare Diseases

Involved partners: ELIXIR-NL: UM, RUMC

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Abstract

The ELIXIR Service Bundle for Systems Biology for Rare Diseases is a collection of available information, tools and data including tutorials and supportive materials to facilitate research and training. In this service bundle we provide this material for five specific use cases that are most common in rare disease research in the systems biology domain.

Introduction

“Systems biology is a means of understanding the dynamic interactions between the components of a living system and, also, between living systems and their interactions with the environment.”

[Definition from: ERASysBio (European Research Area for Systems Biology) initiative]

This service bundle collects a group of use cases on systems biology for rare disease studies and provides possible solutions with workflows and software tools including available tutorials and additional information. In the rare disease field, a common problem is the small population size with often high variability that leaves classical statistics methods with non-significant results. Stratification strategies and data analysis methods based on more in-depth molecular knowledge are one strategy to overcome this hurdle but to be able to use these methods, the biomolecular knowledge needs to be available for data analysis. Capturing, integrating and developing methods to use this knowledge is therefore a major challenge in working with rare disease data.

Use cases for this service bundle are listed here as follows:

1. Rare disease pathways – identifying and integrating knowledge on rare disease molecular pathways
2. Find information about a specific variant from (different) resources
3. Analysis of (multi) omics data and creation and analysis of rare disease networks
4. Integration of toxicology, lifestyle, and nutrition data
5. FAIR data and workflows

1. Rare disease pathways – identifying and integrating knowledge on rare disease molecular pathways

This part of the service bundle describes how to capture molecular, biomedical knowledge on how genes, transcripts, proteins, and chemical compounds interact for normal or abnormal physiological processes. In short, how to create a molecular pathway.

Figure 1: Workflow for the creation of a molecular pathway.

Molecular pathways for rare diseases (WikiPathways environment)

There are different pathway editors currently available. One of them is the WikiPathways environment. WikiPathways is a Wiki based database, an open, community created and expert curated database for biological pathways [<https://www.wikipathways.org/>]. Anyone interested can create and upload a pathway on WikiPathways while a team of curators and automated curation tools regularly check the submissions. WikiPathways content is available under a liberal licence and there are different access and download formats available. The pathway editor for WikiPathways is PathVisio, a Java based editor tool. BridgeDb is an identifier mapping tool that works in the background of WikiPathways and PathVisio to enable the search function for molecular entities and their identifiers.

Tool name [publication]	website	bio.tools	tutorial/documentation
WikiPathways [link]	https://www.wikipathways.org/	https://bio.tools/wikipathways	https://tess.elixir-europe.org/content_providers/wikipathways
PathVisio [link]	https://pathvisio.org/	https://bio.tools/pathvisio	https://pathvisio.org/tutorials https://tess.elixir-europe.org/materials/how-to-make-a-new-pathway-for-wikipathways-using-pathvisio
BridgeDb [link]	https://www.bridgedb.org/	https://bio.tools/bridgedb	https://www.bridgedb.org/pages/docs.html

WikiPathways has different communities for pathways of certain research fields. The rare disease community can be found here:

<https://www.wikipathways.org/communities/rarediseases.html>

PathVisio also allows to visualise (multi) omics data in a pathway from WikiPathways, a tutorial how to do that can be found here:

<https://tess.elixir-europe.org/materials/multi-omics-data-visualization-with-pathvisio>

WikiPathways has several apps to connect to other bioinformatics tools and platforms: rWikiPathways [<https://bio.tools/rwikipathways>] - to use WikiPathways information and data in R. WikiPathways app for Cytoscape [https://bio.tools/wikipathways_app] on e.g. how to create a (rare disease) pathway, visualise omics data, and export it to Cytoscape <https://tess.elixir-europe.org/materials/rare-disease-pathway-and-network-analysis>

Molecular pathways for rare diseases (MINERVA environment)

Another approach to visualise molecular pathways describing a given disorder is to use the MINERVA Platform, a standalone web service for visual analytics for systems medicine diagrams, called disease maps [<https://minerva.pages.uni.lu>]. Such maps hosted on MINERVA can have various architectures [<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37426048/>] with an example of the [CyFi-MAP](#), a map for cystic fibrosis. Recently, a new workflow, called 'automap', is available for MINERVA, allowing faster prototyping of maps for rare diseases. More tools and information <https://disease-maps.org/tools>. Importantly, setup and hosting of disease maps on MINERVA is one of ELIXIR services.

Tool name [publication]	website	bio.tools	tutorial/documentation
The MINERVA Platform [link]	https://minerva.pages.uni.lu/doc/	https://bio.tools/MINERVA_Platform	https://minerva.pages.uni.lu/doc/tutorials/
MINERVA Net [link]	https://minerva-net.lcsb.uni.lu/		https://minerva-net.lcsb.uni.lu/
Automap [link]	https://automap.elixir-luxembourg.org/		https://automap.elixir-luxembourg.org/

2. Find and map information about a specific variant from (different) resources

This part of the service bundle describes resources and strategies about how to find information about a specific genetic variant. There are three basic categories of information on a genetic variant:

1. Identifiers: Which identifier does a specific genetic variant have in a specific variant database and how can we translate between the databases and genome versions?
 - > Annovar, BridgeDb, Ensembl-VEP (incl. VEP Haplosaurus extension) and BioMart, Metadome, and Mutalyzer.
2. Variant classification by variant effect prediction: Is this variant pathogenic or not? Variant effect prediction tools usually deliver numeric or categorical information on the (grade of) pathogenicity.

-> SUSPECT, Ensembl-VEP and its tools: SIFT, CADD, DANN, Fathmm, GAVIN, M-CAP, MutationAssessor, MutationTaster, MutPred2, PolyPhen-2, PON-P2, REVEL, UMD-Predictor, Human Splicing Finder, and VEST.

3. Variant classification by function: Which disease is this variant associated with?

-> Reference data for protein function and links to diseases: Disgenet, Orphadata/genes, neXtProt, ClinVar, HGMD, LOVD, OLIDA (oligogenic diseases database) and DIDA (digenic diseases database).

Figure 2: Possible workflows for different aspects of genetic variant annotation, classification and interpretation.

Tool name [publication]	website	bio.tools	tutorial/documentation
Ensembl-VEP [link]	http://www.ensembl.org/info/docs/tools/vep/index.html	https://bio.tools/vep	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rSIG_OVzyLU
ANNOVAR [link]	https://annovar.openbioinformatics.org/en/latest/	https://bio.tools/annovar	https://annovar.openbioinformatics.org/en/latest/user-guide/startup/#a-useful-tutorial
BridgeDb [link]	https://www.bridgedb.org/	https://bio.tools/bridgedb	https://tess.elixir-europe.org/materials/how-to-install-and-load-the-identifier-mapping-service-with-data-needed-for-gene-to-variant-and-variant-to-gene https://bridgedb.github.io/pages/docs.html
BridgeDbAPI [link]	https://www.bridgedb.org/pages/web-service.html	https://bio.tools/bridgedb_api	https://www.bridgedb.org/pages/tutorials_workflows.html
BridgeDbR [link]	http://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/BridgeDbR.html	https://bio.tools/bridgedbr	http://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/manuals/BridgeDbR/man/BridgeDbR.pdf

biomaRt [link]	https://bioconductor.org/packages/biomaRt/	https://bio.tools/biomaRt	https://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/vignettes/biomaRt/inst/doc/biomaRt.html
MetaDome [link]	https://stuart.radboudumc.nl/metadome/	https://bio.tools/MetaDome	https://stuart.radboudumc.nl/metadome/about
Mutalyzer [link]	https://mutalyzer.nl/	https://bio.tools/mutalyzer	https://mutalyzer.nl/
SUsPECT [link]	GitHub - cmbi/SUsPECT: Variant effect prediction based on custom long-read transcriptomes		https://bmccgenomics.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12864-023-09391-5
DisGeNET [link]	http://www.disgenet.org/	https://bio.tools/disgenet	http://www.disgenet.org/dbinfo
Orphadata [link]	http://www.orphadata.org/	https://bio.tools/orphadata	http://www.orphadata.org/cgi-bin/index.php/
neXtProt [link]	https://www.nextprot.org/	https://bio.tools/nextprot	https://www.nextprot.org/help/simple-search
ClinVar [link]	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/clinvar/	https://bio.tools/clinvar	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/clinvar/intro/
HGMD - Human Genome Mutation Database [link]	http://www.hgmd.org/	https://bio.tools/hgmd	http://www.hgmd.cf.ac.uk/docs/new_help.html
LOVD - Leiden Open Variation Database [link]	http://www.lovd.nl/3.0/home	https://bio.tools/lovd	http://www.lovd.nl/3.0/docs/
DIDA - Digenic Diseases Database [link]	http://dida.ibsquare.be/	https://bio.tools/dida	http://dida.ibsquare.be/documentation/
OLIDA - Oligogenic diseases database [link]	https://olida.ibsquare.be/	https://bio.tools/olida	

3. Analysis of (multi)omics data and creation of RD networks

Multi omics data analysis focuses on identifying functional groups of interest rather than single gene products or metabolites to investigate a disorder (rare disease or any other experimental setup). These functional groups are biological entities linked by their biological or chemical connection, e.g. transcription factor - gene - mRNA expression, or protein (enzyme) - metabolite levels. Depending on the available data, in multi omics analysis it is possible to investigate causes and consequences of up and downstream pathways for changed gene products or metabolites.

There are different ways to approach these analyses from purely statistical methods of data integration (intrinsic methods) to methods including prior knowledge (extrinsic methods), in which the knowledge comes from a large variety of interaction databases (e.d. Drug-target, miRNA - target, or protein-protein-interaction) or gene set databases (e.g. GO).

Figure 3: Exemplimentary workflow for diabetic liver modelling based on pathway and network analysis.

The following intrinsic methods are available for example workflows from WorkflowHub. The workflows have been developed within the EJP RD project and are derived from a dataset with proteomics, peptidomics, and miRNA data.

Tool name [publication]	website	bio.tools	tutorial/documentation workflow
MOGAMUN	https://www.bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/MOGAMUN.html	https://bio.tools/mogamun	https://www.bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/vignettes/MOGAMUN/inst/doc/MOGAMUN_Vignette.html
momix	https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/126		https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/126
mixOmics [link]	http://mixomics.org/	http://mixomics.org/	http://mixomics.org/2019/09/webinar-mixomics-in-50-minutes/ https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/330
WGCNA - Weighted Correlation Network Analysis [link]	https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/WGCNA/	https://bio.tools/wgcna	https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/WGCNA/WGCNA.pdf https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/331

For extrinsic methods, these workflows are available:

- Tutorial for a network biology workflow including pathway and network analysis <https://tess.elixir-europe.org/materials/a-network-biology-workflow-to-study-transcriptomics-data-of-the-diabetic-liver> (see figure)
- Network tutorial <https://coort.gitlab.io/tutorial-network-data/>
- Network inference <https://mkutmon.gitlab.io/tutorial-network-inference/>
- Network algorithms <https://mkutmon.gitlab.io/tutorial-network-algorithms/>
- Systems biology - pathway and network analysis for disease mechanisms <https://mkutmon.gitlab.io/int3007/>

Tool name [publication]	website	bio.tools	tutorial/documentation
Cytoscape [link]	http://www.cytoscape.org/	https://bio.tools/cytoscape	https://github.com/cytoscape/cytoscape-tutorials/wiki
CyTargetLinker [link]	https://cytargetlinker.github.io/	https://bio.tools/CyTargetLinker	https://cytargetlinker.github.io/pages/tutorials
Linkset creator	https://github.com/CyTargetLinker/linksetCreator		https://github.com/CyTargetLinker/linksetCreator
orsum [link]	https://anaconda.org/bioconda/orsum	https://bio.tools/orsum	https://github.com/ozanozisk/orsum/

Not directly relevant for network analysis, but a useful tool is “orsum” - <https://anaconda.org/bioconda/orsum> , a script that allows comparison of results from Gene Ontology overrepresentation analysis based on their GO structure. In the following analysis of a Huntington’s transcriptomics dataset, orsum is used to compare different analysis methods [link to preprint].

There is an extensive collection available of possible gene sets for enrichment analysis:
<https://www.gsea-msigdb.org/gsea/msigdb/human/collections.jsp#C2>

4. Integration of toxicology, lifestyle, and nutrition data

To investigate interactions or overlap between rare disease pathways or networks using any kind of ‘chemical compound information’ is a useful approach for several purposes: 1. Identification of potential drug-target interactions that can be used to identify or prioritise research on treatment; 2. In parallel, identification of potential toxic or adverse interactions of an otherwise useful drug that becomes toxic at lower concentrations due to impaired metabolic or signalling pathways in rare disease patients. 3. Identify potential nutrients that may not be metabolised properly or have a potential for symptomatic treatment; 4. Identify potential environmental compounds that may or may not affect individuals with rare diseases stronger than the healthy population. This kind of analysis usually starts with either a list of differentially expressed genes and a network of interest (e.g. a rare disease pathway or a WGCNA cluster network) (see network biology workflow), but can also directly be derived from gene-disease-association information (RareGenoScope) or vice versa from a list of chemical compounds. To this purpose, ODAMnet will identify potential rare diseases that might be affected by those.

- A general tutorial for a network biology workflow including pathway and network analysis - including network extension with e.g. chemical compounds (drugs, nutrients, toxic compounds). The linksets for the CyTargetLinker app on Cytoscape are available on the CyTargetLinker website [\[https://cytargetlinker.github.io/pages/linksets\]](https://cytargetlinker.github.io/pages/linksets). It is furthermore possible to create new linksets using the Linkset Creator [\[https://github.com/CyTargetLinker/linksetCreator\]](https://github.com/CyTargetLinker/linksetCreator). <https://tess.elixir-europe.org/materials/a-network-biology-workflow-to-study-transcriptomics-data-of-the-diabetic-liver>
- RareGenoScope: a RShiny app to create a protein-interaction network around rare disease genes and identify potential drugs for repurposing (under development) <https://github.com/mehaa6/creating-and-analzing-rare-disease-networks>
- ODAMnet - a python tool to create and investigate a protein interaction network around a (list of) chemical compounds that allows comparison with a rare disease network <https://bio.tools/odamnet>

Tool name [publication]	website	bio.tools	tutorial/documentation
RareGenoScope	https://github.com/mehaa6/creating-and-analzing-rare-disease-networks		
ODAMnet	https://pypi.org/project/ODAMNet/	https://bio.tools/odamnet	https://odamnet.readthedocs.io/en/latest/
Cytoscape [link]	http://www.cytoscape.org/	https://bio.tools/cytoscape	https://github.com/cytoscape/cytoscape-tutorials/wiki

CyTargetLinker [link]	https://cytargetlinker.github.io/	https://bio.tools/CyTargetLinker	https://cytargetlinker.github.io/pages/tutorials
Linkset creator	https://github.com/CyTargetLinker/linksetCreator		https://github.com/CyTargetLinker/linksetCreator

Databases of interest for chemical compound-target interactions:

Tool name [publication]	website	bio.tools	tutorial/documentation
AOPwiki [link]	https://aopwiki.org/ https://aopwiki.rdf.bigcat-bioinformatics.org/	For the RDF: https://bio.tools/aop-wiki_rdf	https://aopwiki.org/info_pages/7
CTD - Comparative Toxicogenomics Database [link]	https://ctdbase.org/		https://ctdbase.org/help/tutorials.jsp;jsessionid=EEA21481CC255CE6873376F3613E00FD
DrugBank [link]	https://go.drugbank.com/	https://bio.tools/drugbank	https://www.drugbank.ca/about
ChEMBL [link]	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chembl/db/	https://bio.tools/chembl	https://chembl.gitbook.io/chembl-interface-documentation/frequently-asked-questions

5. FAIR data and workflows

Making data and workflows FAIRly available is by now required in almost every project. The FAIR Data Cube (FDCube) tool supports this effort by aiding different steps throughout the FAIRification process (Figure 4). To start with, it adopts an investigation-study-assay (ISA) metadata format to annotate the dataset with suitable metadata. Deposition of this metadata to a FAIR data point (FDP) is included in the tool, in order to allow specific searches using the metadata. Last, the FDCube supports the shift in systems biology and other fields towards federated data analysis by the combined use of Vantage6 and Docker to query the data. For workflows, there are databases like WorkflowHub where (FAIR) workflows (in CWL- common workflow language, SnakeMake, or other workflow making tools) can be stored in a version-controlled manner.

Tool name [publication]	website	bio.tools	tutorial/documentation
Fair Data Cube [link]	https://github.com/Xomics/FAIRDataCube		https://github.com/Xomics/FAIRDataCube/wiki
WorkflowHub	https://workflowhub.eu/	https://bio.tools/workflowhub	https://about.workflowhub.eu/

Figure 4: Exemplary FAIR Data Cube (FDCube) workflow, here shown for the Trusted World of Corona (TWOC) dataset.

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